

RURAL WOMEN FARMERS’ EMPOWERMENT THROUGH ACCESS TO AGRICULTURAL INFORMATION: A PANACEA FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN BENUE STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *In Nigeria, agriculture has been at a subsistence level without a record of any substantial breakthrough in term productivity increase in recent times compared to some few developing nations, despite its role in the nation’s food security. This scenario may continue to linger if the issue of cultural norms and gender inequality infringing on equality of access to agricultural empowerment is not adequately addressed by the government and stakeholders in the sector. The study on rural women farmers’ empowerment through access to agricultural information: A panacea for sustainable development in Benue State, Nigeria aims at investigating sources of agricultural empowerment information, access period to agricultural empowerment opportunities, types of accessible agricultural empowerment to women, organizers of the empowerment training and constraints in accessing agricultural empowerment opportunities by Benue rural women farmers. The survey research design was adopted and three hundred and fifty rural women were randomly sampled for the study. A questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. The finding reveals family, friends, and radio as the main sources of information compare to agricultural extension agents officially saddled with the task of transferring agricultural information research institutes and universities to the grassroots farmers. The study further reveals that rural women are left in ignorance amidst plenty of agricultural information for lack of access due to cultural norms and gender disparities, despite their involvement in agriculture practices. The result uncovers the pain of the rural women farmers’ not being recognized despite their involvement in farming as a profession due to cultural norms and gender inequality. Also, the study finding agrees that occasionally agricultural extension agents organize general agricultural skills empowerment programs with biases, as it tends to favor the men farmers. Researchers recommend that documented policy should be formulated prohibiting inequality access to empowerment opportunities in sensitive sectors like agriculture. Also, suggested the restructuring of agricultural extension service deliveries to rural areas to reflect educational campaigns on cultures that are detrimental to sustainable agriculture and development.*

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Introduction

Information is a strong determinant for knowledge growth, transformation, and development and a tool for human capacity building as it overhauls one mindset with inspiration and pushes for practicability. Yet, sectors and rural areas of most developing nations, precisely Nigeria experiencing economic, health, and agricultural development meltdowns due to information scarcity. Information is an asset to knowledge growth and an enhancer of light from the darkness erected by ignorance. However, Emmanuel and Ekoja (2020) stressed that changing from ignorance to the light of knowledge without adequate information to influence decision-making, will be a mirage. This a clear indication, for government at all levels of government, agencies, and stakeholders responsible for knowledge transfer to modify the modality of their operations without discrimination in disseminating timely information that will influence positive change in Nigeria citizens.

In Nigeria, agriculture is a vital organ that determines the nation's food security; however, farmers' access to agricultural information is a prerequisite for maintaining sustainable productive development due to the complex nature of the occupation. Access to agricultural information is an energizer to farmers as it endows them with the knowledge that bridges their knowledge gap. Also, Sanusi, Peti-Ibikunle, and Mshelia (2010) added that dissemination of agricultural Information is

very crucial to the agricultural productivity of farmers because it is the only means by which they can learn innovations that improve their productivity. In other words, tolling with their information availability and accessibility means jeopardizing the nation's survival as a well-fed nation translates to productive citizens. Information is a resource that influences the determination of any person or group of persons to arrive at the attainment of set goals (Emmanuel, 2022). Attaining sustainable product development in Nigeria will entail equal access to undistorted timely information by all categories of farmers without disparities or cultural biases. Nkechi and Oyemike (2015) are of the view that the agriculture sector thrives based on the availability of relevant agricultural information that is associated with the needs of those in the agricultural sector.

In most rural areas of Nigeria, agricultural empowerment opportunities are rarely accessed by farmers, most especially women farmers due to cultural beliefs, norms, and other factors, despite their women's indelible contribution to sustainable agriculture. Karim, Lindberg, and Wamala (2017) agree that rural women lack access to basic assets and social rights due to the patriarchal nature of some communities which hinders their full participation in agricultural production and the developmental process. Also, Studies by Doss, 2002; Ani, 2004; and Fontana, 2009 in Mbah, Chia, and Ezeano, 2017 noted that rural women are usually disadvantaged in access to all factors of

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production and processing despite their involvement in farming generally. Peacock (2005) asserted that agriculture-led development is fundamental to reducing hunger and poverty (70% of which is the rural areas), generating economic growth, reducing the burden of food imports, and opening the way for the expansion of exports. Similarly, Chuhan-Pole and Angwafo (2011) and World Bank (2012) attested that agriculture plays a pivotal role in national development as it is a major source of employment and a catalyst for gross domestic product (GDP) and wealth creation process in many African countries. All of the above points to the fact that agriculture is a major contributor to the nation's economic growth and development if properly coordinated from formulation of policies down to implementation without gender disparities among the rural farmers.

Agriculture in Nigeria will continue at a subsistence level without any remarkable development until the government and stakeholders in the agriculture sector change their narrative of knowledge transfer to the grassroots farmers in rural areas. Knowing fully well that most food consumed and raw materials used for nations' economic development come from the rural farmers' outputs who are left wallowing in primitive cultural beliefs and gender disparities detrimental to agricultural sustainable productivity. studies by Food and Agriculture Organization (2011); Folbre (2013); World Bank

(2014); Aguilar, Carranza, Goldstein, Kilic, and Oseni (2015); Slavchevska (2015) and Zereyesus (2017) confirms that women provide most of the labour force for agricultural production, yet they lag behind men concerning agricultural productivity due to the gender inequalities that persist in respect of access to, control over and utilization of productive resources such as land, livestock, labour, education, extension and financial services, and technology.

The recognition of rural women farmers' contribution to agricultural development and equal access to empowerment opportunities is a doorway to agricultural breakthroughs. Supporting the preceding view, Aliyu, Garba, and Aminatu (2018) affirmed that boosting women's empowerment is indispensable because women constitute the most viable resource of a nation and important economic power blocks waiting to be tapped in the quest for sustainable development. Also, Ukwoma and Njoku (2013) state that rural women in Nigeria are predominantly involved in agriculture; they produce the food for the citizenry and they should be well-armed with the necessary information, knowledge, and resources that will assist them, to achieve the goal of improved agriculture and food security. Axèle and Huaman (2019) state that strengthening the role of women in agriculture could boost agricultural productivity and income, thereby closing the gender gap by ensuring gender equality in access to productive resources would raise agricultural output in developing countries

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and help reduce hunger. Since Njobe (2015) said African women are an integral part of the agricultural sector and spend nearly 60% of their time on agricultural activities. Rural women farmers' empowerment stands as the key to the attainment of productive development. Adding to the submission above, Endalcachew (2016) confirmed that unless women are empowered and gender equality is achieved for women to play their role in economic, agricultural, social, political, and environmental sectors, the country will not achieve sustainable development.

United Nations Women (2020) notes that empowering women is essential, not only for the well-being of individuals, families, and rural communities but also for overall economic productivity. Empowerment is the ability that creates a knowing in people of its surrounding treasures lying dormant waiting to be tapped for a change to erupt. Empowerment occurs when the target group can determine their fates and accomplish their objectives through access and control of resources (Ukwoma and Njoku, 2013).

For, rural women farmers in Nigeria to continue functioning as major producers of food and raw materials in the country, the issue of gender disparity and inequality must be a thing of the past in agriculture, giving way to equal access to all existing agricultural empowerment opportunities at the three tiers of government. Only then, will the role of women farmers' contributions in agriculture be recognized and

equally boost their morale to do more. Rural women farmers are described as farmers putting in all efforts to ensure food is provided for their families and yet lack the recognition of the significant role being played. As, Ozoya (2016) observed that agricultural extension strategies have conventionally focused on increasing the production of cash crops by providing men with training, information, and access to inputs and services to the detriment of women, who produce food crops, thereby limiting their productivity. Therefore, talking of sustainable agricultural development for the nation's food security will remain a dream if proactive actions are not taken to ensure equilibrium access of both men and women farmers to agricultural information and training in rural areas of Nigeria. Udemezue and Odia, (2021) said if gender inequality is minimized and women are given better access to agricultural facilities, achieving food security will be much easier. It has been established over time that raising women's status means poverty declines and nutrition is enhanced.

Lack of sustainable agricultural development in the sector despite the much effort put in by the government and the farmers influences the investigation of rural women farmers' empowerment through access to agricultural information: a panacea for sustainable agricultural development in Nigeria. The study examines sources of agricultural empowerment information, women farmers' access period to agricultural empowerment opportunities, types

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of agricultural empowerment accessible to women, who are the organizers of empowerment training, and lastly constraints in accessing agricultural empowerment opportunities by Benue rural women farmers.

Methodology

The study used a survey research design. Nworgu (2015) observed that survey research is concerned with a systemic description of events as they are because it is aimed at collecting data on something and describing the characteristics and facts about the population of a given study. This makes the design relevant for studying

Table 1: Distribution of Administered Questionnaire to Respondents

S/N	The 2 Local Government Areas	Total Copies of the Questionnaire Administered	Total Copies Retuned
1	Benue	350	337
	Total	350	337

Table 1 above shows the distribution of the questionnaires that were administered to the respondents randomly in the rural areas of the State. Three hundred and fifty (350)

rural women farmers’ empowerment of agriculture for sustainable development in Benue state, Nigeria. Three hundred and fifty rural women farmers were randomly sampled in the State. Questionnaires were used for data collection. Obtained data were analyzed using frequency tables and mean scores of four-scale ratings. That is, any mean score of 2.50 and above is considered positive and accepted and any score below 2.50 is regarded as negative and rejected.

Findings

questionnaires were administered and three hundred and thirty-seven (337) were duly completed and returned, representing a 96.3% response rate.

Table 2: Sources of Agricultural Empowerment Information for Rural Women Farmers

S/N	Sources	Means	Standard Deviation	Rank	Decision
1	Agricultural Extension Agents	1.96	0.9	5 th	Disagree
2	Radio	2.59	1.20	2 nd	Agree
3	Information centres and Libraries	1.83	0.71	8 th	Strongly Disagree
4	Male farmers	2.01	0.94	4 th	Disagree
5	Social Media Platforms	1.92	1.11	7 th	Disagree
6	Family and Friends	2.61	1.26	1 st	Agree

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7	Mobile Phones	2.16	0.90	3 rd	Disagree
8	Community Elders	1.95	0.82	6 th	Disagree

From Table 2, the major sources of agricultural information used by rural women farmers are family and friends, and radio with mean scores of 2.61 and 2.59, compared to the agricultural extension agents saddled with the responsibility of transferring updated agricultural information to the grassroots with a mean score of 1.96. It is more worrisome that the custodians and disseminators of information (information centres and libraries) are not well recognized as sources of information to satisfy the various needs of users, with the lowest mean score of 1.83. From observation, when administering the questionnaire, the facial expression of the

respondents shows that the words libraries and information centres sounded strange to them. This means that the impact of libraries and information centres is not being adequately felt at the grassroots. It should be noted that although the farmers were not literate in the English language, most of them learned in their local language. The implication is that libraries and information centres which are specialized in gathering and repackaging information (including translation to local languages) can leverage their being literate in their local languages to reach out to these rural women farmers.

Table 3: Rural Women Farmers’ Access Period for Information on Agricultural Empowerment Opportunities

S/N	Access to Information Opportunities	Means	Standard Deviation	Rank	Decision
1	Daily	1.65	0.47	5 th	Disagree
2	Weekly	1.51	0.50	6 th	Disagree
3	Forth Nightly	1.66	0.59	4 th	Disagree
4	Quarterly	1.76	0.94	3 rd	Disagree
5	Annually	2.13	1.15	2 nd	Disagree
6	Not at all	2.51	1.19	1 st	Agree

Table 3 shows that rural women farmers in the study areas lack access to information on agricultural empowerment opportunities with a “not at all” mean score of 2.51 while other periods of access to information included annually, quarterly, fortnightly, weekly, and daily with mean scores of 2.13, 1.76, 1.66, 1.51 and 1.65 respectively. The result demonstrates

clearly that rural women farmers are wallowing in ignorance of available agricultural information despite their major involvement in agriculture practices due to biases in access to information. The impeded access to agricultural information by women is the reason why agricultural growth in Nigeria is lagging behind other countries which are committed to

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channeling the unimpeded flow of agricultural information regularly to both men and women.

Table 4: Types of Agricultural Empowerment Opportunities Accessible to Rural Women

Farmers					
S/N	Available Opportunities	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank	Decision
1	Indigenous Adaptation Strategies / Climate Change Empowerment	2.09	0.72	4 th	Disagree
2	Agro-Implements Empowerment	2.33	0.95	1 st	Disagree
3	Agricultural Credit Facilities Empowerment	2.04	0.94	5 th	Disagree
4	Farm Inputs Empowerment	2.28	1.05	2 nd	Disagree
5	Current Practices in Agricultural Empowerment	2.14	0.74	3 rd	Disagree
6	Human Capacity Building/ Agricultural Skills Transfer	1.84	0.89	7 th	Disagree
7	General Agricultural Education Empowerment	1.96	0.95	6 th	Disagree

Table 4 shows rural women farmers’ disagreement with benefiting from the types of agricultural empowerment opportunities listed in Table 4. These included agro-implements empowerment, farm inputs empowerment, current practices in agriculture, indigenous adaptation strategies/climate change empowerment, agricultural credit facilities empowerment, general agricultural education empowerment and human capacity-building/educational skills transfer with a mean score of 2.33, 2.28, 2.14, 2.09, 2.04, 1.96 and 1.84 respectively.

Table 5: Organizers of Information on Agricultural Empowerment Opportunities for Rural Women Farmers

S/N	Organizers	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank	Decision
1	Agricultural Extension Agents	1.80	1.03	5 th	Disagree
2	Entrepreneurs	2.11	0.89	3 rd	Disagree
3	Libraries/ Information Centre	2.14	2.17	2 nd	Disagree
4	NGOs	2.55	1.05	1 st	Agree
5	School Educators	1.93	0.86	4 th	Disagree

Table 5 shows the categories of agricultural empowerment opportunity providers. The table indicates non-governmental organizations (NGOs) with a mean score of 2.55 as the main provider of agricultural empowerment

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opportunities while agricultural extension agents ranked lowest with a mean score of 1.80.

Table 6: Rural Women Farmers' Constraints in Accessing Agricultural Empowerment Opportunities

S/N	Constraints	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank	Decision
1	Low-Level Education	2.38	1.05	3 rd	Disagree
2	Cultural Biases	2.86	0.93	1 st	Agree
3	Lack of Awareness of Opportunities Available	2.06	0.76	4 th	Disagree
4	Gender Disparities	2.77	0.94	2 nd	Agree
5	Lack of Rural Women Farmers' Interest in Empowerment Opportunities	1.74	0.79	5 th	Disagree

Table 6 shows rural women farmers' constraints in accessing agricultural empowerment opportunities. The table shows cultural biases as the highest constraint to accessing information on empowerment opportunities with a mean score of 2.86. This was followed by gender disparities with a mean score of 2.77 while lack of interest in empowerment opportunities was the least with a mean score of 1.74.

Discussion

Sources of Agricultural Empowerment Information for Rural Women Farmers

The study indicates that family and friends, and radio were their major sources of information compared to the agricultural extension agents officially saddled with the responsibility of transferring agricultural research output information to the grassroots farmers and communicating the farmers' challenges back to research institutes for further research work. This makes it worrisome because of the significance of these women in agriculture

which requires that they should be fully informed about all activities that increase production. The study is in line with that of Nkechi and Oyemike (2015) who noted that the agriculture sector thrives based on the availability of relevant agricultural information that is associated with the needs of those in the agricultural sector. A major finding in one of the local governments studied, women engaged more in farming occupation with greater passion compared to men, yet their sources of information is a major challenge. To surmount the challenge of the availability of agricultural information to farmers, stakeholders responsible for channeling information must adhere to the study of Sanusi, Peti-Ibikunle, and Mshelia (2010) that observed dissemination of agricultural information is very crucial to the agricultural productivity of farmers because it is the only means by which they can learn innovations that improve their productivity.

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Rural Women Farmers’ Access Period to Information Agricultural Empowerment Opportunities

The result without doubt shows that rural women are left in ignorance amidst plenty of agricultural information for lack of access attributed to cultural norms and gender disparities, despite their involvement in agriculture practices. The study is of the view that Nigeria, will continue to lag in agricultural growth and never attain productive sustainability with impeded agricultural information flow to rural women farmers. In a similar view, Karim, Lindberg, and Wamala (2017) affirmed that rural women lack access to basic assets and social rights due to the patriarchal nature of some communities which hinders their full participation in agricultural production and developmental process. Also, FAO, (2014) observed that rural women in agriculture do not have equal access to land rights, education, agriculture training, seeds, water, or tools. They also lag behind their male counterparts in accessing information, training, and the latest technologies.

Types of Agricultural Empowerment Opportunities Accessible to Rural Women Farmers

The majority of rural women farmers in the area of study are at a disadvantage in benefiting from agricultural empowerment opportunities available due to some cultural norms and gender inequality. The women also lamented their efforts not being recognized despite

ensuring that food is provided for the families, although, their impact would have been felt if only they are empowered occasionally like the men farmers. On the hand, Arthur, Kwarteng, and Dorinaa (2016) noted the need to disseminate information to everybody through town criers and radio stations without discrimination. This will help empower the women as information birth knowledge empowerment.

Organizers of Information on Agricultural Empowerment Opportunities for Rural Women Farmers

NGOs are the main organizers of agricultural empowerment opportunities. However, agricultural extension agents occasionally organize general agricultural skills empowerment programs in favour of the men farmers. This confirmed what Ozoya (2016) observed that agricultural extension strategies have conventionally focused on increasing the production of cash crops by providing men with training, information, and access to inputs and services to the detriment of women, who produce food crops, thereby limiting their productivity. The result makes it worrisome as the agencies such as libraries and extension agents charged with the responsibility of mediating between research institutes and universities are found wanting in discharging their duties to the rural areas of the nation. As very few respondents attested that the concept of agricultural extension agents/services is not new to them but they had a contrary opinion of

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libraries and information centres. The study agrees with Emmanuel and Ekoja (2020) that confirms most rural dwellers' are not aware of the concept library and information centres nether the services they provide. This is a challenge for the librarians' profession to awaken to its responsibility of problem identifiers and solvers by providing rural women farmers with the information needs to address the issue of inequality in accessing empowerment opportunities in agriculture to promote their relevance.

Rural Women Farmers' Constraints in Accessing Agricultural Empowerment Opportunities

Cultural biases and gender disparities are the main factors that constrained rural women farmers' access to information on agricultural empowerment opportunities. This also affected their interest in striving to be empowered. This finding is in line with the study of Acha (2016); and Ogunlela and Mukhtar (2009) who attested to the fact that the prevailing gender inequality that dominates the sector places rural women farmers at a disadvantage and limits their productivity and opportunities. Also, Arthur, Kwarteng, and Dorinaa (2016) added lack of access to information and training women's participation in farmer training is low due to the lack of awareness, societal barriers, and transportation facilities.

Recommendations

Researchers recommend that documented policy should be formulated prohibiting

inequality access to empowerment opportunities in sensitive sectors like agriculture, knowing its significance on the nation's economy, development, and food security sustainer. Also, suggested the restructuring of agricultural extension service deliveries to rural areas to reflect educational campaigns on cultures that are detrimental to sustainable agriculture and development.

Librarians and information managers integrate branding and marketing the relevance of services in rural areas to inform mindset change in people with their resources well simplify for comprehension, understanding, and application.

Conclusion

In conclusion, information is the driver of any meaningful impact that will translate to a lifelong change in the individuals' and societies' craving for lasting development. It is important to note that information is valuable when it is timely and loses its worth when it is late. Since information assumed the position of influencing change, government, stakeholders, agricultural extension workers, librarians, and information managers must rethink their service operations to trigger acceptance and a welcoming idea of equality of access to agricultural information/empowerment opportunities. This is because limiting access to agricultural information to men alone will mean resisting sustainability and development in agriculture since rural women farmers are major contributors to the sector.

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Also, the dream of using agriculture to diversify the mono-income generation of oil in Nigeria is only attainable when the significance of rural women farmers is recognized by mitigating some of the cultural beliefs and norms that encourage gender disparities by ensuring that the government develops appropriate policies. Amazingly, in an age where information is available at the tip of our fingers, it is disheartening to note that rural women farmers are still wallowing in the dark for relevant information. This is causing gross setbacks in their massive role in agriculture which might otherwise be laudable. This situation provides a negative impression about librarianship and information managers as they are found wanting in the discharge of their duties as disseminators and custodians of information that address the needs of users

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